

Proniosomal Gels: A Novel Vesicular Approach for Controlled and Targeted Drug Delivery

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, vesicular drug delivery systems have emerged as effective alternatives to traditional formulations, addressing challenges related to stability, targeting, and controlled release. Among these, proniosomal gels have attracted considerable attention due to their improved stability, ease of preparation, and ability to encapsulate both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs. Proniosomes are dry, anhydrous systems mainly composed of non-ionic surfactants, cholesterol, and stabilizing agents, which transform into niosomes upon hydration to provide sustained and localized drug release. Several preparation techniques such as coacervation phase separation, slow spray coating, and slurry methods offer formulation flexibility and scalability. Their lamellar bilayer architecture enhances drug loading and skin permeation efficiency. Proniosomal gels exhibit multiple advantages, including prolonged stability, prevention of aggregation and leakage, and convenient storage and handling. Physicochemical assessments like pH, viscosity, entrapment efficiency, and diffusion studies validate their performance. These systems have shown promising applications in managing hypertension, diabetes, hormonal imbalance, and peptide-based therapies, as well as in topical and cosmetic formulations. Ongoing research focuses on improving large-scale production, incorporating herbal and nutraceutical compounds, and extending their therapeutic potential for chronic and dermatological disorders. Overall, proniosomal gels serve as an innovative, biocompatible, and efficient approach for achieving controlled and targeted drug delivery.

Keywords: Proniosomal Gel, Niosomes, Targeted Drug Delivery, Vesicular drug delivery system, Controlled release.

INTRODUCTION

In recent times, no single drug delivery system has been able to meet all the desired criteria; however, efforts have been made to address this through novel approaches. To accomplish either targeted or controlled delivery, numerous innovative methods covering a range of administration routes have emerged. The major goals of innovative drug delivery are to minimize adverse effects and maintain a steady and effective drug level in the body. It also uses drug carriers to target drug delivery and localize the drug activity. One method of vesicular drug delivery involves encapsulating the medication in liposomes, niosomes, transferosomes, pharmacosomes, and pro-vesicles like proliposomes and proniosomes. Liposomes and niosomes have an advantage over other traditional dosage forms because of their

particle nature, which serves as a drug reservoir. In order to modify the pattern and the drug release, a few changes can also be made. Additionally, it was discovered that the modified vesicles have characteristics that allowed them to effectively transport medications into the skin's deeper layers.¹

Compared to conventional dosage forms, vesicular drug delivery systems that use colloidal particle carriers, like liposomes or niosomes, offer clear advantages. Although the materials used to formulate proniosomes make them more stable and provide many more benefits than liposomes and niosomes, proniosomal gels share structural similarities with liposomes and niosomes, both of which have a bilayer. Proniosomes offer further simplicity in dosing, distribution, storage, and transportation while mitigating the physical stability issues of niosomes,

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such as leakage, fusion, and aggregation. Due to their nonionic nature, proniosomes have low toxicity and can entrap hydrophilic and lipophilic medicines in vesicular membranes or aqueous layers. Proniosomes are dry formulations that can be rehydrated with a quick stir in hot water and metered as needed.²

PRONIOSOMAL GEL

Proniosomal gel is a semi-solid, liquid crystalline formulation composed of non-ionic surfactants. It can be prepared by dissolving the surfactant in a small quantity of suitable solvent along with a minimal amount of aqueous phase.³

Proniosomes are vesicular drug delivery systems consisting of non-ionic surfactants, cholesterol, and various additives. They are dry or anhydrous formulations produced by coating a carrier with non-ionic surfactants.⁴

These structures represent liquid crystalline, compact hybrids of niosomes, which can either be readily converted into niosomes upon hydration or used directly for topical or transdermal applications. Proniosomal gels generally exhibit a transparent, translucent, or white semisolid appearance, providing excellent physical stability during both storage and transportation.²⁸

Formation of Niosomes from Proniosomes:

Proniosomes are converted into niosomes upon hydration, leading to the formation of multiple multilamellar vesicles. Hydration can occur either through contact with the skin's moisture or by using aqueous or aqueous-based solutions. Proniosomes are capable of encapsulating both hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs. Experimentally, niosomes can be generated from proniosomes by adding the drug-containing aqueous phase to the proniosomal mixture. During this process, the mean phase transition temperature of the surfactant and the degree of agitation are carefully controlled to ensure proper vesicle formation.

STRUCTURE OF PRONIOSOMES

Proniosomes are semisolid gel-like structures that consist of a mixture of liquid crystal phases, including lamellar, cubic, and hexagonal forms. They typically

have lamellar structures within the microscopic size range. Proniosomes are prepared using non-ionic surfactants and cholesterol. The hydrophobic portion of the non-ionic surfactant faces inward, while the hydrophilic portion orients outward, forming a bilayer. When incorporating drugs, hydrophilic drugs are encapsulated within the aqueous core of the vesicles, whereas hydrophobic drugs are embedded within the bilayer of the proniosomes.⁴

Proniosomes can be either uni-lamellar or multilamellar, depending on the method of preparation. They consist of a surfactant bilayer, with the hydrophilic ends oriented toward the interior and exterior of the vesicle, while the hydrophobic chains face each other within the bilayer. This structure allows hydrophilic drugs to be encapsulated in the aqueous core, whereas hydrophobic drugs are incorporated within the lipid bilayer.⁹

Fig. 1: STRUCTURE OF PRONIOSOMES

ADVANTAGES OF PRONIOSOMAL GELS

Proniosomal gels are capable of entrapping a wide range of active compounds. Easy to transport, sterilize, store, distribute, and dose. Protects drugs from degradation caused by hydrolysis or oxidation. No special storage or handling conditions are required. Prevents issues such as sedimentation, aggregation, or leakage. Requires minimal and acceptable amounts of solvents during preparation. Enables controlled, targeted, and sustained drug release due to depot formation.⁸

MECHANISM OF VESICLE FORMATION IN PRONIOSOMES

Vesicle formation in proniosomes relies on the ability of non-ionic surfactants to form bilayer vesicles rather than micelles. This ability is influenced by three key parameters: The hydrophilic-lipophilic balance (HLB) value of the surfactant. The chemical structure of the components. The critical packing parameter (CPP).

Proniosomes tend to form vesicles similar to niosomes. The CPP describes the relationship between a surfactant's structural features—specifically, the size of its hydrophilic head group and the length of its hydrophobic alkyl chain—and its tendency to form vesicles.

When CPP values range between 0.5 and 1, the surfactant is likely to form vesicles. A CPP below 0.5 favors the formation of spherical micelles, whereas a CPP above 1 tends to produce inverted micelles, which may eventually lead to precipitation. All Spans share the same hydrophilic head group but differ in their alkyl chain lengths.

TYPES OF PRNOSOMES

Proniosomes are classified based on the type of carrier employed and the method used for their preparation.

1. Dry granular proniosomes
2. Sorbitol based proniosomes
3. Maltodextrin based proniosomes
4. Liquid crystalline proniosomes

SORBITOL BASED PRNOSOMES

Sorbitol-based proniosomes are dry formulations where sorbitol acts as the carrier material, coated with a layer of non-ionic surfactant. Upon the addition of hot water and gentle agitation, these proniosomes rapidly convert into niosomes. They are typically prepared by spraying a surfactant solution (prepared in an organic solvent) onto sorbitol powder, followed by solvent evaporation. Since sorbitol is soluble in organic solvents, the spraying and evaporation process is repeated until a uniform surfactant coating is obtained. Sorbitol-based proniosomes exhibit a uniform size distribution and are particularly useful for drugs that are prone to hydrolysis. However, residual sorbitol can reduce the entrapment efficiency to nearly half compared to other carriers, necessitating

a reduction in the carrier proportion in the final niosomal suspension. A major challenge in their preparation lies in analyzing sorbitol particles, as sorbitol is soluble in chloroform and other organic solvents. These proniosomes are commonly prepared using the slow spraying method.

MALTODEXTRIN-BASED PRNOSOMES

Maltodextrin-based proniosomes are prepared using the fast slurry method, where the preparation time is independent of the surfactant-to-carrier ratio. This technique allows the formation of proniosomes with a high surface area-to-carrier ratio. Converting these proniosomes into niosomes for drug delivery is a straightforward process. In a similar approach using sorbitol, a solid surfactant-sorbitol cake is formed. However, since the morphology of maltodextrin is maintained, hollow maltodextrin particles can be utilized to achieve a significant increase in surface area. This increased surface area leads to a thinner surfactant coating, enhancing the efficiency of the rehydration process. This preparation method holds great potential for the delivery of hydrophobic and amphiphilic drug molecules due to its improved surface characteristics and simplicity.²⁹

LIQUID CRYSTALLINE PRNOSOMES

Liquid crystalline proniosomes are specialized vesicular systems formed when surfactants interact with water, causing their lipophilic chains to undergo a transformation into a disordered, fluid-like structure called the lyotropic liquid crystalline phase. This transformation can be achieved through three primary mechanisms: first, by increasing the temperature to the surfactant's Kraft point, where micelle formation begins; second, by adding a solvent that dissolves and liquefies the lipid components; and third, by employing a combination of both elevated temperature and solvent addition. Within this liquid crystalline state, the surfactant molecules arrange themselves into a lamellar phase, characterized by overlapping lipid bilayers separated by thin aqueous layers. These highly organized structures can be identified by their distinct X-ray diffraction patterns and appear as thread-like formations when observed under a polarized light microscope.

Also referred to as proniosomal gels, liquid crystalline proniosomes serve as effective drug reservoirs for transdermal drug delivery. In practical applications, such as transdermal patches, the system typically consists of an aluminum foil backing for support, adhered to a plastic sheet of suitable thickness. The proniosomal gel is uniformly spread over the plastic layer and then covered with a fine nylon mesh to protect and stabilize the formulation. This design ensures a controlled release of the drug through the skin.

The advantages of liquid crystalline proniosomes are significant. They exhibit excellent physical stability, which enhances shelf life and handling. Their structure allows for substantial drug entrapment efficiency, meaning a higher amount of the active pharmaceutical ingredient can be loaded and retained within the vesicles. Additionally, these proniosomes inherently enhance skin penetration, improving the delivery of drugs through the tough barrier of the skin. The preparation process is straightforward and easily scalable, eliminating the need for complex or lengthy manufacturing steps. Furthermore, the use of liquid crystalline proniosomes avoids the inclusion of inappropriate or potentially harmful pharmaceutical excipients, making the system safer and more compatible for various therapeutic applications. Overall, these features make liquid crystalline proniosomes a promising and versatile carrier system for efficient and effective transdermal drug delivery.²¹

COMPONENTS OF PRNOSOMAL GEL

SURFACTANTS

The HLB value of the surfactants is used to choose the ones for proniosomes. The surfactants thought to be most conducive to proniosome formation have an HLB value between 4 and 8. When hydrated, the hydrophilic surfactants with high aqueous solubility do not reach a concentration point that could cause coalescence and aggregation. For instance, proniosomes are formed by using polysorbate 20 as a surfactant with cholesterol. The surfactant's HLB value influences the extent of drug entrapment. The drug entrapment is also influenced by the surfactant's transition temperature. The maximum drug entrapment efficiency is exhibited by surfactants with a higher transition temperature. Greater penetration

and a bigger area exposed to the skin are the effects of these surfactants' higher HLB values, which also reduce surface free energy and enable the creation of larger vesicles (proniosomes).¹⁰

STABILIZERS

Cholesterol: The best encapsulation efficiency for hydrophilic drugs is shown by the Tween series of surfactants, which have a long alkyl chain and a large hydrophilic group in a 1:1 ratio with cholesterol. Additionally, it has been noted that adding cholesterol improves the stability of vesicles. Its primary function is to stabilize membranes. A naturally occurring steroid that is added to membranes is cholesterol. Through electrostatic or repulsive steric effects, it stabilizes the system and prevents vesicle fusion or aggregation. In the niosomal system, it results in the transition from a gel state to a liquid phase.¹¹

Lecithin: One of its main constituents is phosphatidylcholine. Lecithin is an additional stabilizer that can be utilized in the proniosome preparation process. It is not very soluble in water. Lecithin functions as a permeation enhancer in proniosomes and causes vesicles to shrink in size because of hydrophobicity. Even though lecithin's drug entrapment efficiency is lower than cholesterol.⁴

CARRIERS

The manufacture of proniosomes using maltodextrin allowed for flexibility in the ratio of surfactant to other ingredients. Furthermore, it improves surface area and, thus, loading efficiency. The carriers should be free-flowing, non-toxic, and safe. They should also have good water solubility for convenient hydration and poor solubility in the loaded mixed solution. The following are examples of commonly used carriers: lactose, glucose, sorbitol, mannitol, and sucrose stearate.⁶

HYDRATION MEDIUM

By adding an appropriate hydration solution, such as water or phosphate buffer saline, niosomes can be formed from proniosomes. Proniosome entrapment efficiency and vesicle size are impacted by hydration media.³²

SOLVENTS AND AQUEOUS PHASE

Alcohol: The choice of alcohol significantly influences vesicle size and drug entrapment efficiency. Among the various alcohols, ethanol is considered the most suitable solvent for proniosome preparation. Due to its high water solubility, ethanol tends to produce vesicles of a larger size compared to other solvents such as butanol or isopropanol.

Aqueous Phase: The aqueous phase used for proniosome formation typically includes phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), hot water, or glycerol.

MISCELLANEOUS COMPONENTS

Dicetyl phosphate (DCP): It serves as a lipid component in proniosome formulation. Incorporating DCP can enhance drug entrapment slightly more than using cholesterol and surfactant alone.

Stearyl amine: Stearyl amine, another charged lipid, tends to reduce the entrapment efficiency when used in the formulation.⁴

Solulan: Solulan C24 (poly-24 oxyethylene cholesteryl ether) is added to the formulation to ensure it remains homogeneous and free from aggregates.⁸

METHODS OF PREPARATION OF PRNIOSOMAL GEL

1. Coacervation phase separation.
2. Slow spray coating method.
3. Slurry method.

COACERVATION PHASE SEPARATION

The coacervation phase separation process can be used to prepare proniosomes. In this method, appropriate quantities of non-ionic surfactants, lecithin, cholesterol, and the selected drug are combined in a clean, dry, wide-mouth glass container. A suitable volume of organic solvent, such as absolute ethanol, is added, and the mixture is gently warmed in a water bath until the surfactants are completely dissolved. The combination is then heated until a clear solution is achieved by adding a warmed aqueous phase, usually a phosphate buffer with the appropriate pH. A proniosomal gel is formed when the resulting dispersion is allowed to cool at room temperature.⁵

This approach doesn't require any specialized equipment and is quick and easy. It prepares gels using coacervation phase separation techniques and is especially useful for low-dose formulations or small quantities that are usually manufactured at the laboratory scale.²¹

SLOW SPRAY COATING METHOD.

This method involves the preparation of proniosomes by spraying a surfactant dissolved in an organic solvent onto a suitable carrier material, followed by evaporation of the solvent. As the carrier material is soluble in the organic solvent, the process is repeated several times until the desired surfactant loading is achieved. The surfactant forms a thin coating over the carrier surface, which upon hydration, produces multilamellar niosomes as the carrier dissolves. The resulting niosomes are comparable to those obtained by conventional methods, exhibiting a more uniform size distribution. This formulation technique is particularly advantageous for the encapsulation of hydrophobic drugs, enhancing their stability and preventing hydrolysis.⁶ A drawback of the spray-coated method is the abrasion or wear of carrier particles that occurs when the surfactant is applied at high speeds.²¹

SLURRY METHOD

An appropriate amount of carrier material, such as maltodextrin, is placed in a round-bottom flask, and the surfactant solution is progressively added to produce a homogeneous slurry. If necessary, more organic solvent can be added to attain the desired consistency. The flask is then connected to a rotating evaporator and vacuum until the powder is dry and free-flowing. The proniosome powder is then stored in sealed containers in the refrigerator. The preparation time is largely independent of the ratio of surfactant solution to carrier material and can be increased as needed.⁷ The slurry method offers the advantage of using maltodextrin as a carrier, which is highly water-soluble and effective in this role. Because the coating on the carrier is uniform and standardized, simply adding surfactant dissolved in an organic solvent helps protect both the drug and surfactants from oxidation and hydrolysis. However, this method has some drawbacks, including being time-consuming and requiring specialized equipment.

Additionally, it is best suited for fixed batch sizes, which may lead to repeated product loss during production.²¹

FACTORS AFFECTING FORMULATION OF PRONIOSOMES

The properties of proniosomes are influenced by a variety of formulation and processing factors. These consist of the length of the surfactant chain, the amount of cholesterol, the drug concentration, the concentration of total lipids, the charge of lipids, the pH of the dispersion medium, and the kind of alcohol that was employed in the process.⁴

Chain Length Of Surfactant: Proniosomes are frequently prepared using spans. The alkyl chain that is connected varies in the variety of spans. The entrapment efficiency is improved by lengthening the surfactant chain. Span 60 (C18) > Span 40 (C16) > Span 20 (C12) is the order of Spans' entrapment efficiency.

Amount Of Cholesterol: Both permeability and entrapment efficiency are impacted by changes in cholesterol level. Raising the cholesterol level improves entrapment efficiency and creates a hard layer or encapsulating proniosomes, which reduces vesicle permeability and stops medication leakage.

pH of the Hydration Medium: The efficiency of encapsulation is also influenced by the pH of the hydration liquid used to convert proniosomes to niosomes. encapsulation efficiency was shown to rise when the pH was lowered from.⁴

Total Lipid Concentration: The encapsulation efficiency is positively affected by the amount of lipid concentration. The efficiency of encapsulation rises with an increase in lipid concentration.⁸ As lipid concentration rises, the percentage of lipid participating in encapsulation falls.

Drug Concentration: Both the percentage encapsulation efficiency and the amount of drug encapsulated per mol total lipids upon hydration and niosome formation increase with increasing concentration of lipids in the proniosomes.

Charge of the Lipids: The percentage encapsulation efficiency of flurbiprofen into niosomal vesicles was reduced by the addition of either stearylamine (SA), which produces a positive charge, or diethyl phosphate (DCP), which produces a negative charge.⁸

EVALUATION OF PRONIOSOMAL GEL

Physical Appearance And Homogeneity: Visual observations were used to assess the prepared gels' homogeneity and physical characteristics after they had been placed in the container. Their appearance and the presence of any aggregates were examined.¹²

STABILITY STUDIES

The stability study followed the ICH recommendations. The proniosomal gel formulations were stored in sealed glass vials at room temperature ($25\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) and in the freezer ($4\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$). After six months, formulations were tested for entrapment efficiency and vesicle size.¹³

% Entrapment Efficiency: To determine the percentage of EE, 20 mg of Proniosomes were placed in a beaker and dissolved in 20 ml of buffer pH 5.8 and ethanol co-solvents. Using ultra-centrifugation, the free butenafine hydrochloride was extracted from proniosomes for 30 to 45 minutes at 40 degrees Celsius at a speed of 14,000 RPM. To ascertain the quantity of free medicine in the formulations, 1 milliliter of the supernatant was collected following centrifugation and examined at 223 nm using a UV spectrophotometer.¹⁴

pH Measurement: The digital pH meter was used to measure the gel's pH. After dissolving 0.1 g of gel in 10 ml of distilled water, the electrode was dipped into the gel formulation, and a continuous reading was recorded. The readings were taken for an average of three times.²

Viscosity: The viscosity of proniosomal gel is typically measured using a Brookfield Viscometer, employing a spindle at a temperature of $25\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The appropriate spindle and revolutions per minute (RPM) are selected through a trial-and-error method. Viscosity determination involves testing various spindle numbers at different speeds. The preferred spindle and RPM correspond to a torque range of 20%

to 100% for accurate viscosity measurement. The gel is placed in a jar, and the spindle is positioned vertically, ensuring it does not touch the bottom of the jar. The viscosity of the proniosomal gel is then recorded.²¹ To assess consistency, a swamp channel a cone-shaped molded pipe with a small drag tube on the base end that allows mud to flow under gravity head is used.¹⁵

Scanning Electron Microscopy And Size Analysis

(Sem): Proniosome particle size is an important consideration. SEM was used to observe the proniosomes size distribution and surface appearance. Proniosomal powder was applied on aluminum stubs that had double-sided tape attached to them. The aluminum stub was stored in the scanning electron microscope's vacuum chamber. Using a gaseous secondary electron detector, the samples' morphological characteristics were investigated.¹⁶

Optical Microscopy: In a glass tube, 0.2 g of proniosome gel with varying drug loads was diluted with 10 ml of pH 7.4 phosphate buffer. A few drops of the resulting niosomal dispersion were spread on a glass slide and examined for the presence of insoluble drug crystals using an ordinary light microscope at 10 and 40 magnification powers. (40). Photomicrographs were taken using a digital camera.¹⁷

Measurement Of Vesicle Size: Measurement of vesicle size is primarily used for characterizing the size and shape of vesicles. The proniosomal powder was hydrated with phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) and then subjected to bath sonication for 3 minutes. The resulting dispersion was used for size determination. Vesicle size was measured using a particle size analyzer, which employs a HeNe laser beam with a wavelength of 632.8 nm and a minimum power of 5 mW, focused by a Fourier lens (R-5) onto the center of a small volume sample cell equipped with a multielement detector. Prior to measurement, the samples were stirred to ensure uniformity.

In Vitro Drug Release: In vitro drug release can be carried out using dialysis tubing. The proniosomes are placed inside prewashed dialysis tubing, which is then sealed. This proniosomal suspension-filled dialysis bag is tied to a glass tube and immersed in a beaker containing 50 ml of phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), serving as the receptor compartment. Samples are

withdrawn from the medium at predetermined intervals and analyzed using UV spectrophotometry.²⁶

Zeta Potential: Zeta potential analysis is performed to evaluate the colloidal properties of the prepared formulations⁸. PCS measured the zeta potential using the Malvern Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malvern Instruments). To measure proniosomal gel formulations, hydrate them and dilute samples with distilled water¹⁸. The charge on the vesicles and their mean zeta potential values, along with the standard deviation from five measurements, were obtained directly from the analysis.⁸

Drug Content: Approximately 100 mg of proniosomes are diluted in methanol and shaken for at least 15 minutes. This mixture is then further diluted to a total volume of 100 ml with methanol. From this solution, 10 ml is taken and further diluted with phosphate buffer. The resulting sample is then analyzed using a UV spectrophotometer to measure absorbance, which is used to calculate the drug content.⁴

Osmotic Shock: Determining vesicle size variations is aided by an osmotic shock research. This is accomplished by incubating the proniosomal formulations for three hours in various solutions, such as hypertonic, isotonic, and hypotonic solutions. Using an optical microscope, vesicle size changes are identified.³⁰

Spreadability: To test the spreadability of vesicular gel formulations, 0.5 g of each gel was deposited in a 1 cm diameter circle on a pre-marked glass plate, which was then covered by another glass plate. A weight of 500 g was placed on the upper glass plate for approximately 15 seconds.¹⁹

In Vitro Diffusion Studies: In vitro diffusion investigations were performed to guarantee that the medication was released from the gel. The Franz diffusion cell was utilized to create the drug release profile. The dialysis membrane was soaked overnight in phosphate buffer with a pH of 7.4. The dialysis membrane was clamped between the donor and receiver compartments; 10 mg of Fenopropfen Calcium Equivalent Gel was placed in the donor compartment, and 100 ml of phosphate buffer 7.4 pH was added to the receiver compartment. The mixture

was swirled constantly at 50 rpm with a magnetic bead and kept at $37^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ throughout the experiment. To maintain the sink condition, 1 ml of the samples were taken from the receiver compartment at intervals of 1 hour, 2 hours, 3 hours, 4 hours, 5 hours, 6 hours, 8 hours, 12 hours, 16 hours and 24 hours and replaced with 1 ml buffer. Then an appropriate dilution was prepared to collect UV absorbance, and then the absorbance was taken, and the percentage cumulative drug release was computed.²⁰

APPLICATIONS

Proniosomal gels are a promising alternative to niosomes for delivering actives to specific locations. Proniosomes can be hydrated with aqueous solutions or by the skin when applied topically. Incorporating these chemicals into a base gel, cream, or ointment creates a cosmetic formulation. These cosmetic compositions can be utilized for topical/transdermal treatments with many functionalities. Proniosomal gel formulation offers benefits for regulated drug delivery, increased bioavailability, fewer side effects, and trapping of both hydrophilic and hydrophobic pharmaceuticals. Proniosome gel's affinity for biological membranes enhances actives' penetration through skin.⁷

CLINICAL APPLICATIONS:

Applications in cardiology: Proniosomes are utilized for transdermal administration of captopril to treat hypertension. The study found that the proniosomal system extends medication release in the body. The medication is encapsulated using sorbitol esters, cholesterol, and lecithin.

Application in diabetes: Furosemide proniosomes skin penetration method involves the usage of span, soya, lecithin, diacetyl phosphate, and cholesterol. Overall, studies indicate that proniosomes provide noninvasive administration of furosemide.¹

Uses in Studying Immune Response: Proniosomes are utilized in immune response studies because of their immunological selectivity, low toxicity, and enhanced stability. They help in investigating the nature of immune reactions triggered by various antigens.

Transdermal Drug Delivery Systems: One of the key advantages of proniosomes is their ability to significantly improve drug absorption through the skin. Proniosomal technology is widely applied in transdermal drug delivery, particularly in the cosmetics industry, where it was among the earliest uses of niosomes. Proniosome-encapsulated antibiotics are also used topically to treat acne, showing much better skin penetration compared to drugs that are not encapsulated. Recently, proniosomal technology has been explored for delivering transdermal vaccines. Along with liposomes and transferosomes, proniosomes have potential for topical immunization, such as with tetanus toxoid. However, current proniosomal formulations tend to induce only a weak immune response.

Localized Drug Action: Proniosome-based drug delivery is an effective strategy to achieve localized drug action because their size and limited ability to penetrate epithelial and connective tissues help retain the drug at the site of administration. This localized delivery enhances the drug's efficacy and potency while minimizing systemic toxicity. For example, antimonials encapsulated in proniosomes are preferentially taken up by mononuclear cells, leading to targeted drug localization, increased potency, and a reduction in both the required dose and associated toxicity. Although proniosomal drug delivery technology is still in its early stages, it shows promising potential as a localized drug delivery system.¹⁸

Delivery of peptide drugs: The disadvantage of oral peptide medication administration is that it bypasses the enzymes that break down the peptide and protein connections. Niosomes were found to be effective in protecting peptides from gastrointestinal degradation. Oral administration of a vasopressin derivative entrapped in niosomes demonstrated that drug entrapment dramatically boosted peptide stability.

Hormonal therapy: Work was done on proniosome-based transdermal administration of levonorgestrel, an emergency contraceptive. The niosome's structure was liquid-crystalline compact hybrid. The system was examined for particle size, encapsulation effectiveness, stability, and in vivo/in vitro studies. A

bioassay for progestational action was also conducted. It contained an endometrial assay as well as the inhibition of corpora lutea formation.²⁶

Sustained release: Niosomes can provide sustained release for medications with low therapeutic index and water solubility, allowing them to remain in circulation.²⁷

Targeting of bioactive agents: One of the most useful properties of proniosomes is their ability to deliver drugs to targeted areas. Drugs can be delivered to the reticulo-endothelial system using proniosomes. The reticuloendothelium system (RES) preferentially absorbs proniosome vesicles. Opsonins are circulating blood factors that regulate proniosome ingestion. Drugs with this location are used to treat malignancies in animals that have already spread to the liver and spleen. The pharmaceutical location can also be used to treat liver parasite infections. Drugs can also be delivered to organs other than the RES via proniosomes. Because immunoglobulin readily attaches to the lipid surface of proniosomes, a carrier system (like antibodies) can be attached to them to direct them to a specific organ.

Proniosomes as carriers for hemoglobin: According to a study by Moser et al. (1989), which used niosomes as a carrier for hemoglobin in the blood, proniosome vesicles can be used to carry hemoglobin in anemic individuals since they are permeable to oxygen.

Cosmetic delivery: L'Oreal's cosmetic applications were the first to report on non-ionic surfactant vesicles. In the 1970s and 1980s, L'Oréal created and patented niosomes. Lancôme debuted the first product, Niosome, in 1987. Niosomes can improve the stability of entrapped medications, raise the bioavailability of poorly absorbed substances, and improve skin penetration, which are all benefits of employing them in cosmetic and skin care applications.³¹

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Proniosomes have grown in prominence in pharmaceutical research due to their capacity to target specific organs or tissues and improve therapeutic effects.²³ Proniosomal formulations are effective for

delivering a variety of pharmaceuticals, including anti-inflammatory, antiviral, anti-infective, antihypertensive, and anti-cancer drugs. Innovative proniosome-based delivery techniques for cosmetics, nutraceuticals, herbal actives, and synthetic formulations require further investigation. Herbal drug is used to prepare proniosomes, decreasing side effects²⁴. When applied topically, proniosomal gel can effectively treat melanoma, psoriasis, bacterial and fungal infections. More study is needed to fully grasp the potential of this new drug delivery technique²⁵. Proniosomal carriers can effectively transport drugs with strong side effects, increasing therapeutic efficacy while reducing unwanted effects. However, there are other problems that must be investigated in the industrial system to demonstrate the ability for the delivery of a diverse range of pharmaceuticals and natural products.²³

CONCLUSION

Proniosomal gels are a potential and innovative way to topical drug delivery, with benefits including increased drug stability, controlled and prolonged release, greater skin penetration, and simplicity of application. Proniosomes serve an important role in transdermal medicine administration due to their great penetration, low toxicity, and controlled release properties²¹. Proniosomes provide numerous advantages, including regulated and prolonged drug release, increased stability, and versatility as drug delivery vehicles. They are regarded as attractive carriers for future pharmaceutical applications due to their excellent physical and chemical stability, as well as their commercial scalability.

Proniosomal systems are especially successful at delivering amphiphilic medications. Their beneficial nature, ability to improve skin penetration via surfactants, and ability to change drug release patterns have made them more appealing for transdermal drug delivery. Proniosomes, when dried, are easily formed into unit dose forms such as beads, pills, or capsules⁸. The system's great stability further supports proniosomes potential for systemic medicinal administration²². Proniosome studies imply that biocompatible carrier materials could be used for future preparation. Future research will look at the

usefulness of combining proniosomes with drugs with specific restrictions to improve therapy outcomes⁸.

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